

**THE PLOT OF FIRST LOVE IN THE NOVELS "ASYA" BY I.S.
TURGENEV AND "OLESYA" BY A.I. KUPRIN**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the consideration of the theme of the first love of Asya and Olesya - heroines of the eponymous novels by I.S. Turgenev and A.I. Kuprin.

Key words: Turgenev, Kuprin, Asya, Olesya, Mr. N.N, Ivan Timofeevich, first love, separation, "Turgenev's girls".

Ivan Sergeyevich Turgenev was a Russian realist writer, poet, essayist, playwright, prose writer and translator. One of the classics of Russian literature. The author of such works as: "Rudin", "The Nest of the Nobility", "On the Eve", "Fathers and Children", "Notes of a Hunter", "First Love", "Asya", "Veshnye Vody".

Alexander Ivanovich Kuprin was a Russian writer best known for his novels *Duel* (1905) and *The Pit* (1915), as well as his novels *Moloch* (1896), *Olesya* (1898), *Captain Rybnikov* (1906), *Emerald* (1907), and *The Pomegranate Bracelet* (1911), filmed in 1965.

The question of the similarity of Turgenev's and Kuprin's works has not been raised very often in literary studies, but it is obvious that there are such elements in the works of the writers, thanks to which we manage to raise this problem again. In their works, similar motifs, characters and types of heroes, as well as character, i.e.

the influence of Turgenev on Kuprin, are noticeable.

By Turgenev's prose we understand not only the cultural-ideological conflict that is established around everything new, or the nobleman's cultural-heroic novel, but also, of course, the narratives of first love. The main theme of Turgenev's and Kuprin's works, which brings closer and clearly shows the similarity of the works "Asya" and "Olesya", is first love. The heroes Mr. N.N, Dmitry Sanin, Turgenev's girl (Asya, Gemma), femme fatale (Polozova, Irina) are filled with romantic pathos, social traits, they are emotionally colored and psychologically expressed.

Speaking of borrowed elements, or Turgenev's traditions in Kuprin's work, one can definitely see the above-mentioned types of characters, plots and motifs, not to mention the titles of the writer's novels from the turn of the 19th to the first third of the 20th century. The objects of analysis are two novels: "Asya" by I.S. Turgenev and "Olesya" by A.I. Kuprin. First of all, the titles of the novels immediately catch the eye. We can unmistakably call them similar: they are the names of the main heroines, but the narrative is told on behalf of a young man.

Asya and Olesya are classic Turgenev girls. Both of them are open, ardent, endowed with extraordinary and attractive beauty, dark hair and fire in their eyes. Their fates are tragic: since childhood they are not always understood by other people, and therefore live isolated from society. Nevertheless, the heroines are pure and truly sincere. However, the "Turgenev's girl" is not the only type of hero that creates an echo of both novels, because we can also note the similarity of the main characters - Mr. N and Ivan Timofeevich. Both of them are quite young and rich, self-confident, their eloquence is appealing, but they also have some discrepancy between what is said and what is done, as Chernyshevsky writes, "a trashy impotence of character". It is from this weakness of character that the girls suffer, and it is also from this weakness that the newly budding relationships between the young people, Aseya with Mr. N. and Olesya with Ivan Timofeyevich, die.

It may be added that the time of action of the main events takes place in the warm season. In "Olesa" it is spring, and in "Asa", presumably, it is spring or fall.

It should be noted that Kuprin's story begins in winter, but after meeting Olesya, the time of year immediately changes to spring.

The idea to create the story "Asya" appeared at Turgenev thanks to his vivid imagination. Once, walking through the streets of a German town, the writer noticed this picture: in the window of the first floor of one of the houses sat an elderly woman, and from the second - looked out a little girl. Turgenev tried to imagine what kind of life these people might have lived. This story formed the basis of the future story. The fate of the heroine Asya was more than fiction to the author.

The work "Asya" Turgenev originally conceived as a story, but in the process of writing it was transformed into a full-fledged novella. The author with great sensitivity and care described the inner world of the characters, found words to convey their feelings and subconscious reactions. Therefore, critics noted the psychologism of the narrative. The work is written in realistic traditions, but the main heroine Asya is a romantic character. The author emphasized her delicate nature - sincere and direct. This makes her a classic "Turgenev's young lady".

A.I. Kuprin's story "Olesya" was created under the direct impression of the author himself from his stay in the Polesie hinterland in the spring of 1898. This area struck the writer with a sharp contrast of social and natural factors that determined the way of life and manners of local residents. This is largely due to the specificity of the genre of the work - a combination of essay and love story. It should be noted that the author in many ways inherits the traditions of Russian realistic prose, which is reflected in the composition, methods of creating images and stylistics.

The story reveals the theme of love and the capacity for self-sacrifice. Olesya is able to love unconditionally and self-sacrificially. Ivan finds in Olesya what he lacks in the world around him - spiritual richness and inner beauty. The main conflict of the work is the confrontation between civilization and the natural world. Society is not ready to accept Olesya, and therefore cannot understand their love with Ivan. According to critic I. G. Chesnokova, far removed from nature

"civilized" people do not recognize anything that goes beyond their ideas about the world. Thus, in Kuprin's story, people raised by nature and engaged in witchcraft turn out to be better and more moral than those who grew up in the "noble" conditions of civilization and interpret the morality of orthodoxy. To the last one wants to believe that a happy ending awaits the lovers. But this does not happen. The girl is forced to leave the village and forever separated from Ivan.

The finale of both novels is unfortunate: it shows the disappearance of the girls, regret for the lost opportunities of young people who end up with only a memory and longing for lost opportunities. There are many such examples. Asya and Olesya are close to Turgenev's Gemma ("Veshnye Vody"), Elena Stakhova ("On the Eve"), Sulamif. Mr. N. and Ivan Timofeyevich are close to Romashov ("Duel") and Dmitry Sanin ("Veshnie Vody").

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